

P revention of endocarditis among dental patients with cardiovascular diseases

Prevención de endocarditis en pacientes odontológicos con enfermedades cardiovasculares

Naira Elshadovna Ramazanova

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Bakinskaya 121, 414000, Russia, ari_rne@icloud.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2756-5611>

Irina Sanalovna Buvaeva

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Bakinskaya 121, 414000, Russia, buvaeva.i02@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-7022-1077>

Navruza Rustamjon kizi Kholmanova

The Pavlov First Saint Petersburg State Medical University, L'va Tolstogo str. 6-8 Saint Petersburg, Russia 197022, navruzakholmanova@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4556-8075>

Daniil Alekseevich Shvedov

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» Medical Faculty, 414000, Astrakhan, Bakinskaya str., 121, daniilshvedov@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6970-5503>

Andrei Vasil'evich Iakovlev

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Bakinskaya 121, 414000, Russia, Y_ako_v@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2484-7998>

Dzhamalutdin Salautdinovich Daudgadzhiev

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Bakinskaya 121, 414000, Russia, gapizov999@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8378-4206>

Bair Sanalovich Menkeev

Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Bakinskaya 121, 414000, Russia, menkeev.bair@bk.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3452-4236>

Received: 11/20/2024 Accepted: 02/19/2025 Published: 03/12/2025 DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14910973>

Abstract

Endocarditis poses a serious threat to patients with cardiovascular diseases, especially in the setting of dental treatment, which can lead to bacterial infection. The purpose of this article is to analyze current approaches to the prevention of endocarditis in this group of patients. The risks associated with invasive dental procedures, the pathogenesis of infective endocarditis, and recommendations for antibacterial prophylaxis are reviewed. Special attention is given to standards proposed by international associations, including the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA). Data on antibiotic choice, timing of antibiotic use, and duration of course are provided. For maximizing patient safety, importance of a multidisciplinary approach, including close collaboration between dentists and cardiologists is emphasized.

Keywords: endocarditis, prophylaxis, dental treatment, cardiovascular diseases, infective endocarditis, antibacterial prophylaxis, multidisciplinary approach.

Resumen

La endocarditis representa una grave amenaza para los pacientes con enfermedades cardiovasculares, especialmente en el contexto del tratamiento dental, que puede provocar una infección bacteriana. El propósito de este artículo es analizar los enfoques actuales para la prevención de la endocarditis en este grupo de pacientes. Se revisan los riesgos asociados con los procedimientos dentales invasivos, la patogénesis de la endocarditis infecciosa y las recomendaciones para la profilaxis antibacteriana. Se presta especial atención a los estándares propuestos por asociaciones internacionales, incluidas la Sociedad Europea de Cardiología (ESC) y la Asociación Estadounidense del Corazón (AHA). Se proporcionan datos sobre la elección de antibióticos, el momento de su uso y la duración del tratamiento. Para maximizar la seguridad del paciente, se enfatiza la importancia de un enfoque multidisciplinario, que incluya una estrecha colaboración entre dentistas y cardiólogos.

Palabras clave: endocarditis, profilaxis, tratamiento odontológico, enfermedades cardiovasculares, endocarditis infecciosa, profilaxis antibacteriana, abordaje multidisciplinario.

Infective endocarditis is a dangerous infectious disease associated with inflammation of the inner lining of the heart¹. For patients with cardiovascular disease, this condition carries a high risk of complications, including thromboembolism, heart failure and death. Of particular importance in the prevention of endocarditis is the proper organization of dental treatment, as invasive interventions can cause bacteremia leading to the development of the disease.

Current clinical guidelines emphasize the importance of antibiotic prophylaxis to prevent infective endocarditis in patients at risk. At the same time, excessive or inadequate use of antibiotics may contribute to the development of microbial resistance, which requires strict adherence to treatment standards and protocols.

The relevance of this topic is due to the increasing number of patients with cardiovascular pathologies requiring dental care, as well as the need to develop effective interdisciplinary approaches to their treatment. The present work is aimed at analyzing the current strategies of endocarditis prevention related to dental practice and determining the optimal methods of interaction between cardiologists and dentists to minimize the risks.

The following research methods were used to write this paper: analysis and synthesis allowed us to study individual aspects of the problem, for example, to identify risk factors for endocarditis or to assess the impact of various dental procedures on the development of the disease, and to combine the obtained data into a single concept of prevention.

Generalization was used to summarize the results of previously conducted studies and to form universal conclusions: thus, on the basis of recommendations of international organizations, the principles of antibacterial prophylaxis were generalized.

The classification method was used to systematize data on dental procedures, risk of infective endocarditis or different antibiotic groups. The comparative method made it possible to compare different approaches to prevention, such as the recommendations of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA).

Endocarditis is a dangerous inflammatory disease of the inner lining of the heart (endocardium) that most often develops as a result of bacterial infection. Patients with cardiovascular disease have a significantly increased risk of its occurrence, especially when factors such as heart defects, artificial valves, or previous episodes of infective endocarditis are present. One of the key pathways for pathogens to enter the bloodstream is invasive dental procedures such as tooth extraction, endodontic treatment, or procedures involving manipulation of gingival tissue².

Dental treatment involving trauma to the oral cavity can cause bacteremia, the entry of bacteria from the oral cavity into the bloodstream. In healthy patients, this phenomenon most often passes without trace, but in people with cardiovascular disorders, such microorganisms can settle on the endocardium or artificial heart valves, causing infection. The development of infective endocarditis carries a high mortality rate and a significant risk of complications, including thromboembolism, sepsis and irreversible cardiac dysfunction.

Therefore, prevention of endocarditis in patients with cardiovascular diseases requiring dental care is a crucial task. The problem is complicated by the need to strike a balance: on the one hand, effective prevention of bacterial complications is required, and on the other hand, the risks associated with the unnecessary use of antibiotics, such as the development of antibiotic resistance and side effects, need to be minimized³.

Current clinical guidelines developed by international associations emphasize the need for antibacterial prophylaxis for certain groups of patients during dental procedures. It is important that dentists and cardiologists work closely together to develop an individualized prophylaxis plan for each patient. This helps to reduce risks and increase the safety of medical interventions.

Thus, endocarditis occurring against the background of dental procedures requires a comprehensive approach to prevention, including careful risk assessment, strict adherence to modern protocols and interdisciplinary interaction between specialists.

Modern approaches to the prevention of infective endocarditis in patients with cardiovascular diseases are based on a combination of scientific data, international clinical recommendations and practical experience of physicians of various specialties⁴. The main aspects of prevention include identification of risk groups, use of antibacterial drugs, individualization of treatment ap-

proach and emphasis on interdisciplinary cooperation. The definition of patient risk groups is presented in Table 1.

The risks associated with invasive dental procedures in patients with cardiovascular disease are an important aspect in treatment planning because they can lead to serious complications such as infective endocarditis. The main risks can be divided into several categories.

One of the main risks is damage to oral tissues. In invasive dental procedures such as tooth extraction, implants or gum surgery, trauma to mucous membranes or soft tissues can occur. This opens the door for bacteria from the mouth to enter the systemic bloodstream, creating a risk of bacteremia. Bacteria in the bloodstream can reach the heart and settle on the endocardium or artificial valves, contributing to the development of infective endocarditis⁵.

Another significant risk is bacteremia, which is the entry of bacteria into the bloodstream. Invasive procedures, especially those involving disruption of the integrity of mucous membranes or gums, can cause microscopic pores in tissues through which bacteria from the oral cavity enter the bloodstream. For healthy individuals, such bacteremia does not usually cause serious consequences, but in patients with cardiovascular disease, especially those with heart defects or artificial valves, this infection can lead to endocardial infection.

An equally important factor is the patient's systemic cardiovascular disease. The presence of heart defects,

artificial valves or other diseases of the cardiovascular system increases the susceptibility of the organism to infections. Patients with such diseases have weakened defense mechanisms, making them more vulnerable to the development of infective endocarditis, especially if their heart valves or other structures are susceptible to damage.

Poor oral hygiene is also an important risk factor. Poor hygiene and the presence of inflammatory gum disease such as periodontitis create conditions for bacteria to multiply in the oral cavity. Such bacteria can enter the bloodstream even during minor manipulations such as brushing or flossing, increasing the likelihood of bacteremia and, consequently, infective endocarditis⁷.

Finally, lack of prophylaxis is one of the most significant causes of risk. Patients at risk should receive antibiotic prophylaxis before invasive dental procedures. Failure to do so can lead to infection and the development of endocarditis. It is important that both dentists and cardiologists clearly follow existing protocols and guidelines for the prevention of infective endocarditis to minimize the risk of this disease among patients with cardiovascular pathologies.

Thus, all these risks emphasize the importance of a comprehensive approach to the management of dental patients with cardiovascular disease, including timely diagnosis, prevention, and multidisciplinary specialist collaboration to ensure patient safety.

Table 1. Risks associated with invasive dental procedures

Risk category	Description	Examples
Damage to oral tissues.	Trauma to the mucous membranes and gums opens the way for bacteria to enter the bloodstream.	Extraction of teeth, surgical treatment of gums.
Bacteremia	The entry of bacteria from the oral cavity into the systemic bloodstream.	Invasive procedures such as dental implants.
Oral pathogenic flora	Presence of bacteria with high infectious potential in the oral cavity.	<i>Streptococcus viridans</i> , <i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i> .
Systemic cardiovascular factors	Increased susceptibility due to the presence of heart defects or prosthetic valves.	Artificial valves, congenital heart defects.
Poor oral hygiene	Increased bacterial load on the background of inflammation and gum disease.	Periodontitis, deep caries.
Lack of prevention	Failure to use antibiotics in at-risk patients.	Skipping taking antibiotics before tooth extraction.

The pathogenesis of infective endocarditis is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Pathogenesis of infective endocarditis

Stage	Description	Key events and mechanisms
1- Bacteraemia The entry of bacteria from the mouth or other sources of infection into the bloodstream.	The entry of bacteria from the mouth or other sources of infection into the bloodstream.	Invasive dental procedures (e.g. tooth extraction, implants) can cause tissue trauma and bacteria can enter the bloodstream.
2. Damage of the endothelium.	Microorganisms settle on damaged parts of the endocardium or artificial valves.	Artificial valves, damaged areas of the heart (e.g. due to a heart defect) provide conditions for bacteria to attach.
3. Microbial adhesion	The bacteria firmly attach to the surface of the valves or endocardium, forming a biofilm.	Bacteria such as <i>Streptococcus viridans</i> attach to damaged tissue and form a biofilm, making them resistant to immune response and antibiotics.
4. Multiplication of microorganisms	Bacteria begin to actively multiply, creating vegetations - clusters of microorganisms and platelets.	Bacterial multiplication in biofilm leads to the formation of vegetations that can block normal valve function.
5. Development of inflammation	An inflammatory response begins in the body in response to infection, which can lead to tissue damage.	Inflammation in response to bacterial infection can lead to damage to heart tissue, valves, and blood vessels.
6. Thrombosis	The formation of blood clots on the vegetations can lead to thromboembolisms and other complications.	Vegetations on the valves can become a source of thrombosis, increasing the risk of embolism to various organs (e.g., brain or kidneys).

The pathogenesis of infective endocarditis includes several consecutive stages that begin with the entry of bacteria into the bloodstream and end with the development of inflammation, thrombosis, and possible serious complications⁸. Each of these stages plays an important role in the development of the disease, especially among patients with cardiovascular pathologies, where the risk of infection is significantly increased.

The first step in pathogenesis is bacteremia, i.e. the entry of microorganisms into the bloodstream. In the case of invasive dental procedures such as tooth extraction, implants, or surgery, oral tissues are traumatized, creating conditions for bacteria normally residing in the oral cavity to enter the bloodstream⁹. Although bacteremia may be asymptomatic in healthy individuals, in patients with a predisposition to infections or with pre-existing cardiovascular problems, this process can lead to more serious consequences.

Once the bacteria enter the bloodstream, the next step is damage to the endothelium. The endocardium, the inner lining of the heart, plays a key role in regulating processes related to blood flow and valve function. In people with heart defects, artificial valves or other heart abnormalities, the structure of the endocardium can be damaged. Bacteria that enter the bloodstream can settle on these damaged areas, creating ideal conditions for their further growth and the development of infection. Particularly vulnerable are artificial valves, which often become attachment points for microorganisms.

Then comes the stage of microbial adhesion, when bacteria deposited on the endocardium begin to firmly attach to its surface. This process occurs due to the interaction between the cell surfaces of the bacteria and the damaged endocardial tissue. One of the best known

causative agents of infective endocarditis is the bacterium *Streptococcus viridans*, which is often found in the oral cavity. When the bacterium attaches itself to tissue, it begins to multiply vigorously, forming colonies called biofilms. The biofilm serves as a defense for the bacteria because it interferes with the body's immune system and makes the bacteria more resistant to impact of antibiotics¹⁰.

When bacteria begin to actively multiply, they create vegetations - clusters of microorganisms, immune system cells and platelets that form on the surface of valves or other areas of the endocardium. The vegetations can interfere with the normal function of the heart valves, causing them to dysfunction, and can also lead to mechanical damage to the heart, which can impair its ability to pump blood efficiently. Such vegetations can significantly affect cardiac function, leading to various clinical manifestations of infective endocarditis, such as fever, heart murmurs, and dyspnea.

In parallel with the multiplication of microorganisms, an inflammatory reaction develops. In response to infection, the immune system triggers an inflammatory process, the purpose of which is to localize the infection and eliminate the bacteria. However, this process is not always limited to localized changes in the heart. Inflammation can spread to other organs such as the kidneys, lungs or brain, especially if the infection spreads through the bloodstream¹¹. Chronic inflammation can cause tissue damage, which in turn leads to further deterioration of the function of heart valves and other cardiac structures.

The last important step in pathogenesis is thrombosis. Vegetations on the heart valves, consisting of bacteria, platelets and immune system cells, can be a source of thrombosis. The clots that form on these vegetations can

break off and enter the bloodstream, causing thromboembolisms - blockages of blood vessels in various organs. Thromboemboli can lead to severe complications such as stroke, myocardial infarction, thrombophlebitis and other diseases, depending on which organ is embolised.

Thus, the pathogenesis of infective endocarditis is a complex and multifaceted process that begins with the

entry of bacteria into the bloodstream and ends with serious complications such as thromboembolism and chronic heart failure¹². An important aspect in preventing this disease is early diagnosis and adequate prophylaxis, especially in patients with cardiovascular disease who are at high risk.

Recommendations for antibacterial prophylaxis are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Recommendations for antibacterial prophylaxis of infective endocarditis among dental patients

Criteria for prescribing prophylaxis	Type of dental procedure	Drugs and dosage	Features and times of admission
Patients with artificial heart valves	All invasive dental procedures (tooth extraction, implants, periodontal surgery, etc.).	Patients with artificial heart valves All invasive dental procedures (tooth extraction, implants, periodontal surgery, etc.). Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. If allergic to penicillins - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults Antibiotics are taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.	Antibiotics are taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Patients with a history of infective endocarditis	All invasive procedures such as tooth extraction, periodontal surgery, implants, etc.,	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	Antibiotics are taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Patients with congenital heart disease	Invasive procedures such as tooth extraction, periodontal surgery, implants, etc.	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	Antibiotics are taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Patients after heart transplantation with valve dysfunction	Invasive procedures (tooth extraction, implants and others)	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	The antibacterial agent is taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Patients with anatomical anomalies of the heart	Invasive dental procedures including tooth extractions, gum surgeries, etc.	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	The drug is taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Patients with severe immunodeficiency (e.g., patients with HIV or after chemotherapy)	All invasive procedures, including dental manipulations that can damage mucous membranes	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	Taking antibiotics 30-60 minutes before manipulation.
Patients with prosthetic joints and other organs	Invasive dental interventions such as tooth extractions, implants and other procedures	Amoxicillin: 2 g for adults, 50 mg/kg for children. In case of penicillin allergy - clindamycin: 600 mg for adults	Antibacterial medication is taken 30-60 minutes before the procedure.
Routine dental procedures	Procedures that do not involve mucosal trauma (e.g., professional dental cleaning)	Antibacterial prophylaxis is usually not necessary unless there are clear signs of gum infection or other disease.	The use of antibiotics is not required except for specific indications.

The criteria for prescribing antibacterial prophylaxis for infective endocarditis in dental patients with cardiovascular disease are determined according to the patient's condition, type of dental procedure, and other risk factors. The main criteria are the presence of artificial valves, history of infective endocarditis, congenital heart defects, anatomical anomalies of the heart, and conditions when the patient is on immunosuppressive therapy¹³.

Patients with artificial heart valves are at increased risk of developing infective endocarditis. Due to the presence of foreign material (artificial valve) on the heart valves, this area becomes vulnerable to bacterial infection. In invasive dental procedures such as tooth extraction or implantation, there is a possibility of bacteria entering the bloodstream, which can lead to valve infection and development of endocarditis¹⁴. Therefore, antibacterial prophylaxis is recommended for these patients before any invasive dental manipulation.

Patients with a history of infective endocarditis also have an increased risk of recurrent disease. If a patient has a history of infective endocarditis, they are more vulnerable to new infections, especially if endocardial or valve injuries are present. In this case, antibiotic prophylaxis should also be administered before dental procedures involving trauma to mucous membranes or skin.

Patients with congenital heart disease are at risk because defects in the heart structure can create conditions for abnormal blood flow and valve damage. Congenital malformations may include abnormalities of the heart valves or vessels that can become attachment points for bacteria. Antibacterial prophylaxis should be administered in such cases, especially for invasive oral interventions.

Patients with anatomical anomalies of the heart also require antibiotic prophylaxis¹⁵. Anomalies may be congenital or acquired (e.g., after cardiac surgery). Damage to valves or other cardiac structures contribute to an increased risk of infection, as bacteria can easily settle on these damaged areas. Therefore, even relatively simple dental procedures such as tooth brushing or tooth extraction can pose a risk to these patients.

Patients with severe immunodeficiency, such as patients with HIV or those undergoing chemotherapy, should also receive antibiotic prophylaxis. A weakened immune system is unable to fight infections effectively, which increases the risk of infective endocarditis. In these cases, even minor dental procedures can lead to serious infections.

Thus, antibacterial prophylaxis should be individualized according to specific clinical criteria such as the presence of cardiovascular disease, cardiac valve status, patient's immune status, and type of dental procedure. Discussion. Recommendations for antibiotic prophylaxis for infective endocarditis proposed by international associations such as the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA) are

based on a thorough risk analysis and scientific evidence to minimize the possibility of developing this severe disease in patients with cardiovascular disease undergoing invasive dental procedures.

The European Society of Cardiology, in its recommendations for the prevention of infective endocarditis in patients with cardiovascular disease, emphasizes the importance of antibiotic prophylaxis only for those patients at high risk of endocarditis in the event of bacteremia. The ESC focuses on the following key points:

Patients with artificial heart valves should be given antibacterial prophylaxis for invasive dental procedures, as artificial valves are susceptible to bacterial infection¹⁶.

In patients with a history of infective endocarditis, the risk of recurrence is very high and antibiotic prophylaxis before dental interventions is recommended. Prophylaxis before invasive procedures, including dental procedures, is recommended for patients with congenital heart disease.

Patients with transplanted organs, including the heart, due to the possible weakening of the immune system, should receive prophylaxis because they have an increased risk of infection¹⁷.

The ESC also notes that for most other patients who are not at high risk, antibacterial prophylaxis for routine dental procedures is not required. This avoids overuse of antibiotics, which reduces the risk of antibiotic resistance.

The American Heart Association (AHA) proposes stricter criteria for antibiotic prophylaxis for infective endocarditis. The AHA emphasizes the following aspects:

Patients with artificial valves and heart defects should be given antibacterial prophylaxis before any invasive dental procedures such as tooth extractions, implants, and surgeries involving gingival manipulation.

For patients with heart defects who are not candidates for valve replacement, antibacterial prophylaxis is indicated for invasive procedures associated with a risk of bacterial infection.

In patients with chronic conditions such as ischemic heart disease or with valve problems that require intervention, prophylaxis is recommended, especially if the procedure involves disruption of tissue integrity and possible entry of bacteria into the bloodstream¹⁸.

The AHA also notes that antibiotic prophylaxis is not required for less invasive dental procedures (e.g., tooth brushing) in patients at moderate or low risk for infective endocarditis. This direction in the recommendations is aimed at preventing unnecessary prescribing of antibiotics and reducing their side effects.

Both associations agree that antibiotic prophylaxis should be prescribed individually, depending on the clinical situation, the patient's condition and the nature of

the dental procedure. It is important to follow the recommendations to minimize the risk of infective endocarditis while avoiding unnecessary use of antibiotics, which can lead to the development of antibiotic resistance.

An interdisciplinary approach to the management of patients with cardiovascular disease, especially in the context of dental treatment, is key to ensuring patient safety and minimizing the risks of complications such as infective endocarditis. Collaboration between dentists and cardiologists plays an important role in the comprehensive management of these patients, as each specialist brings unique experience and expertise to create an optimal treatment plan¹⁹.

Patients with cardiovascular disease who require dental treatment often have complex and unique medical needs. Cardiologists have in-depth knowledge of the patient's heart condition, diagnoses, medications being taken, and potential risks that may arise from dental interventions. Dentists, on the other hand, must consider the specifics of treatment, such as the need to maintain sterility, use certain medications, or avoid traumatic manipulations that could trigger bacteremia.

Antibiotic prophylaxis is an important aspect of dental interventions in patients with cardiovascular disease, but the administration of antibiotics requires care. Excessive or inappropriate use of antibiotics can lead to the development of antibiotic resistance and other side effects. The cardiologist and dentist, working closely together, can assess the need and dosage of antibiotics based on the patient's condition and avoid overprescribing.

Dental treatment among patients with cardiovascular disease should be coordinated with a cardiologist to avoid the risk of exacerbation of cardiac disease. For example, if a patient is being treated for heart failure or has recently suffered a myocardial infarction, it is important to wait until the patient's condition is stable before performing invasive dental interventions. A cardiologist can help determine the safest time for treatment, and a dentist can help strategize procedures accordingly.

Patients with cardiovascular disease have a higher risk of developing complications during dental procedures, including cardiac arrhythmias, heart attacks or strokes. Collaboration between the dentist and cardiologist can effectively manage these risks. The cardiologist can provide recommendations for monitoring cardiac status during dental interventions, and the dentist can provide an environment for safe performance of procedures by monitoring possible changes in the patient's condition²⁰.

A multidisciplinary approach also includes collaborative patient education. For example, a cardiologist can explain to a patient the importance of following recommendations for the prevention of infective endocarditis and proper oral care to prevent infections, while a dentist can help the patient understand how their treatment can affect their cardiac condition and the importance of safety precautions in the dental practice.

Interdisciplinary collaboration between dentists and cardiologists is integral to the effective and safe treatment of patients with cardiovascular disease. This collaboration helps prevent complications such as infective endocarditis, improve treatment outcomes and enhance patients' quality of life. Close coordination between specialists maximizes patient safety and allows for the most informed and informed decision-making at all stages of treatment.

Conclusions

Patients with cardiovascular disease, especially those with artificial heart valves, those who have undergone cardiac malformations, and those with a history of infective endocarditis, are at high risk for dental interventions. The introduction of bacteria into the bloodstream during invasive dental procedures can lead to infective endocarditis, which requires special attention and preventive measures.

Interdisciplinary collaboration between dentists and cardiologists plays a critical role in ensuring the safety of patients with cardiovascular disease. Collaboration between these professionals allows for correct risk assessment, development of an effective treatment and prevention plan, and proper timing of dental procedures to minimize cardiovascular complications. Each patient with cardiovascular disease has unique medical characteristics, which requires a personalized approach when planning dental treatment. Proper assessment of the patient's condition, selection of appropriate antibiotic prophylaxis, adjustment of drug therapy, and consideration of all risk factors must be individualized for each case.

Prevention of infective endocarditis in patients with cardiovascular disease in the context of dental treatment requires timely administration of antibiotic therapy. The use of antibiotics should be justified, taking into account individual indications and risks, to avoid overuse of antibiotics and the development of antibiotic resistance.

Educating patients with cardiovascular disease is an important tool for preventing infective endocarditis and other complications following dental procedures. Patients should understand the risks associated with bacteremia and follow oral care guidelines to help prevent inflammation of the gums and teeth. It is also important to explain to patients how to properly follow medication recommendations and adhere to preventive measures.

Patients with cardiovascular disease require regular medical monitoring, especially in the postoperative period when there is a risk of complications. The dentist and cardiologist should monitor the patient's condition at

all stages of treatment and after procedures in order to promptly identify and correct possible problems.

Establishing effective communication between cardiologists and dentists contributes to better quality of care and improved outcomes for patients with cardiovascular disease. This approach not only helps prevent infective endocarditis, but also reduces the overall number of complications, improving patients' quality of life.

Prevention of infective endocarditis among dental patients with cardiovascular disease requires a comprehensive approach that includes careful interdisciplinary collaboration among specialists, individualized treatment, adequate antibiotic prophylaxis, and active patient education. Adherence to these principles can reduce the risks and guarantee the safety of dental treatment for this category of patients, contributing to their long-term health and well-being.

References

1. Edozien L C. UK law on consent finally embraces the prudent patient standard. *BMJ* 2015; 350: 2877.
2. Folwaczny M, Bauer F, Grünberg C. Significance of oral health in adult patients with congenital heart disease. *Cardiovasc Diagn Ther* 2019;9:S377-87.
3. Tubiana S, Blotiere PO, Hoen B, et al. Dental procedures, antibiotic prophylaxis, and endocarditis among people with prosthetic heart valves: nationwide population based cohort and a case crossover study. *BMJ*. 2017;358
4. Albes JM. Current practice in prophylaxis of endocarditis: are we running into trouble? *Cardiovasc Diagn Ther* 2018;8:423-31.
5. Mylotte D, Pilote L, Ionescu-Iltu R, et al. Specialized adult congenital heart disease care: the impact of policy on mortality. *Circulation* 2014;129:1804-12.
6. Neidenbach RC, Lummert E, Vigl M, et al. Non-cardiac comorbidities in adults with inherited and congenital heart disease: report from a single center experience of more than 800 consecutive patients. *Cardiovasc Diagn Ther* 2018;8:423-31.
7. Simón-Soro A, Mira A. Solving the etiology of dental caries. *Trends Microbiol* 2015;23:76-82.
8. Talha KM, Baddour LM, Thornhill MH, et al. Escalating incidence of infective endocarditis in Europe in the 21st century. *Open Heart*. 2021;8:e001846.
9. Ramakumar V, Thakur A, Abdulkader R S *et al*. Coronary Stent Infections - A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Cardiovasc Revasc Med* 2023; 54: 16-24.
10. Sanz M, Herrera D, Kebschull M, et al. Treatment of stage I–III periodontitis—The EFP S3 level clinical practice guideline. *J Clin Periodontol* 2020;47:4-60.
11. Bowen WH, Burne RA, Wu H, et al. Oral Biofilms: Pathogens, Matrix, and Polymicrobial Interactions in Microenvironments. *Trends Microbiol* 2018;26:229-42.
12. Cotti E, Mercurio G. Apical periodontitis and cardiovascular diseases: previous findings and ongoing research. *Int Endod J* 2015;48:926-32.
13. Folwaczny M, Wilberg S, Bumm C, et al. Oral Health in Adults with Congenital Heart Disease. *J Clin Med* 2019;8:1255.
14. Frobert O, Lagerqvist B, Olivecrona GK, et al. Thrombus aspiration during ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction. *N Engl J Med*. 2013;369:1587–1597.
15. Horstkotte D, Follath F, Gutschik E, et al. Guidelines on prevention, diagnosis and treatment of infective endocarditis executive summary: the task force on infective endocarditis of the European Society of Cardiology. *Eur Heart J*. 2004;25:267–276.
16. Thornhill M H, Gibson T B, Yoon F *et al*. Endocarditis, invasive dental procedures, and antibiotic prophylaxis efficacy in US Medicaid patients. *Oral Dis* 2023
17. Thornhill M, Prendergast B, Dayer M, Frisby A, Lockhart P, Baddour L M. New evidence calls into question NICE's endocarditis prevention guidance. *Br Dent J* 2024; 236: 702-708.
18. Janszky I, Gemes K, Ahnve S, Asgeirsson H, Moller J. Invasive procedures associated with the development of infective endocarditis. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2018;71:2744–2752.
19. Main B G, Adair S R. The changing face of informed consent. *Br Dent J* 2015; 219: 325-327.
20. Thornhill M H, Dayer M, Lockhart P B *et al*. A change in the NICE guidelines on antibiotic prophylaxis. *Br Dent J* 2016; 221: 112-114.
21. Mosyagin I.G. The role and place marine medicine // *Marine Medicine*. 2023. Vol. 9, № 3. C. 7-12, doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22328/2413-5747-2023-9-3-7-12>
22. Kotovskaya S.V., Boyko I.M., Mosyagin I.G., Khokhrina A.I. The role of a family and a close environment in the formation of the resilience of the extreme activity subjects: cross-sectional study. *Marine medicine*. 2022. Vol. 9, No. 2. P. 98-104, doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.22328/2413-5747-2023-9-2-98-104>
23. Masko E.V., Mosyagin I.G., Boyko I.M. Seasonal dynamics of the functional state of the nervous system of military-age skiers according to visual-motor reaction data // *Marine medicine*. 2022. Vol. 8, No. 3. P. 70–76, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22328/2413-5747-2022-8-3-70-76>.
24. Masko E.V., Mosyagin I.G., Boyko I.M. Bioelectric activity of a brain and cerebral hemodynamics in skiers of military age over seasons of the year // *Marine medicine*. 2022. Vol. 8, No. 4. P. 72–77, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22328/2413-5747-2022-8-4-72-77>.
25. Evdokimov V.I., Mosyagin I.G., Sivashchenko P.P. Primary disease incidence with officers of the Russian aerospace forces and navy (2015–2020) // *Marine Medicine*. Vol. 8, No. 2. P. 38–47. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22328/2413-5747-2022-8-2-38-47>